

WHO HAS FEMALE CHILD?

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Abstract:

The greatest property and prosperity is the child for parents. Some have more children. Some have one child. Some have no child. Some have children earlier. Some have children later. This is due to their previous janma karma. Some have only male children. Some have only female children. They should belong fifth bhava, fifth bhava Lord, which planets occupy the fifth bhava, which Planets aspects fifth bhava and also the strength of Jupiter.

Key Words: Taurus, Cancer, Virgo, Scorpio, Capricorn, Pisces, Female Child, Saturn, Female Sign, Sun, Female Sign, Moon, Female Sign, Mars, Female Sign, Jupiter, Rahu, Kethu, Lagna Lord, Fifth Lord, Female Sign.

Introduction:

The ambition of the human birth is child birth. If one has car, bungalow, diamonds, jewels air conditioners, plasma tv, rupees in crores but has no child is waste. The greatest property in the world is nothing but a child. Some have easily get child. Some have after done pooja and parihars. Someone have child after taken so many medical treatments. Some have child by naturally. Some have child by artificial methods like Intra uterine Insemination (IUI), In Vitro Fertilization (IVF-Test tube baby) and Intra Cytoplasmic Sperm Injection (ICSI). The success rate of artificial methods is very low. People who try the artificial methods spend lot of money and take dangerous hormone based medicines for getting child and mostly get disappointment. Finally they have chosen the option adoption. So child is the most important one in our life.

Rules for Getting a Female Child:

- Rule 1: For getting a female child Mars should stand in Taurus or Cancer or Virgo or Scorpio or Capricorn or Pisces.
- Rule 2: Rahu or Kethu should stand twelveth rasi from Jupiter. It surely gives a female child.
- Rule 3: Rahu conjunctions with fifth Lord and stands in sixth bhava or eighth bhava or twelveth bhava from lagna surely gives a female child.
- Rule 4: The fifth Lord conjunctions with Rahu or moving to touch Rahu as the next planet gives a female baby.
- Rule 5: Lagna Lord or fifth Lord stands in Taurus, Cancer, Virgao, Scorpio, Capricorn or Pisces surely gives a female baby.

We have analysed the above rules with three example horoscopes. If anyone of the rules is found in ones horoscope he/she will have a female child.

Example Horoscope 1:

Name : Gomathi
 Date of birth : 05.03.1973
 Time of birth : 03.00.am.
 Place of birth : Cheyyar
 Gender : Female

		SATURN	KETHU
SUN MOON MERCURY VENUS	RASI		
JUPITER			
ASC MARS RAHU			

MOON JUPITER KETHU	SUN MERCURY	SATURN	
NAVAMSA			
ASC		MARS	RAHU

Rahu Dasa Balance: 1 Year 4 Months 5 Days

S.No	Planet	Standing Star	Padham
1	Lagna	Uthrashada	1
2	Sun	Puratathi	1
3	Moon	Sathayam	4
4	Mars	Pooradam	3
5	Mercury	Puratathi	1
6	Jupiter	Uthrashada	4
7	Venus	Sathayam	2
8	Saturn	Rohini	3
9	Rahu	Pooradam	2
10	Kethu	Arudra	4

In her horoscope

- Jupiter - the lagna Lord stands capricorn gives her a female baby.
- The fifth Lord Mars conjunctions with Rahu gives her a female child.
- Rahu stands in twelfth bhava from Jupiter. It gives her a female baby.

Example Horoscope 2:

Name : Loganathan
 Date of birth : 05.06.1967
 Time of birth : 03.10.pm.
 Place of birth : Madurai
 Gender : Male

SATURN	MOON RAHU	SUN	MERCURY
	RASI		JUPITER VENUS
		ASC KETHU	MARS

	NAVAMSA		SUN MARS RAHU
MERCURY KETHU			
		ASC JUPITER	MOON SATURN

Rahu Dasa Balance: 1 Year 4 Months 5 Days

S.No	Planet	Standing Star	Padham
1	Lagna	Chitra	3
2	Sun	Rohini	4
3	Moon	Bharani	2
4	Mars	Hastha	4
5	Mercury	Arudra	2
6	Jupiter	Pushya	3
7	Venus	Pushya	1
8	Saturn	Uthratathi	2
9	Rahu	Aswathi	4
10	Kethu	Swathi	2

In his horoscope

- Mars stands in twelfth bhava Virgo surely gives him a female baby.
- Lagna Lord Venus stands in eighth bhava Cancer surely gives hime a female baby.
- The fifth lord Saturn stands in sixth bhava Pisces surely gives him a female baby.
- The fifth lord Saturn stands in Uthratathi star second padham and goes to touch Rahu which stands in Aswathi fourth padham.

Example Horoscope 3:

Name : Kavitha
 Date of birth : 28.07.1971
 Time of birth : 03.20.pm.
 Place of birth : Dindigul
 Gender : Female

ASC	SATURN		
MOON RAHU	RASI		
SUN			KETHU
MERCURY	MARS JUPITER VENUS		

VENUS	KETHU	SUN	
	NAVAMSA		ASC
		MOON MERCURY SATURN RAHU	MARS JUPITER

Mars Dasa Balance: 3 Yyear 0 Months 5 Days

S.No	Planet	Standing Star	Padham
1	Lagna	Puratathi	4
2	Sun	Sravana	2
3	Moon	Danishta	3
4	Mars	Anuradha	2
5	Mercury	Puradam	3
6	Jupiter	Anuradha	2
7	Venus	Jyeshtha	3
8	Saturn	Bharani	3
9	Rahu	Danishta	3
10	Kethu	Magam	1

In his horoscope

- Mars stands in the ninth bhava Scorpio surely gives her a female baby.
- The lagna lord Jupiter stands in the ninth bhava Scorpio surely gives her a female baby.
- The fifth lord Moon conjunctions with Rahu in twelveth bhava aquaris. It surely gives her a female baby.
- The fifth lord stands in Danishta second padham and goes to touch Rahu which stands in Danishta third padham. It surely gives her a female baby.

Conclusion:

Male baby or female baby is not a subject. We need only baby. The option male or female is chosen by God. From this article one can.Easily understand the possibility of the baby's gender very well.

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